

Research papers

Influence of equilibration time, soil texture, and saturation on the accuracy of porewater water isotope assays using the direct H₂O(liquid)–H₂O(vapor) equilibration method

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ABSTRACT

The hydrogen and oxygen stable isotopes of water ($\delta^2\text{H}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$) are powerful tracers for studying subsurface water flow processes, but the extraction of porewater from unsaturated soil is complex and laborious. The direct liquid–vapor equilibration method (DLVE) for isotope analysis overcomes this challenge by analyzing headspace vapor in isotopic equilibrium with the porewater under closed system conditions. However, the effect of the equilibration time, soil texture, and porewater saturation on isotopic results is not fully understood yet. We tested three differently textured, disaggregated soils (sandy, silty loam and clay) to assess how the equilibration time is impacted by (i) porewater saturation (100%, 80%, 60%, and 40%), and (ii) soil surface area. For all tests, the water loss through diffusion was negligible (<0.3%). The experiments showed that for disaggregated sandy soil, 24 h was a sufficient isotopic equilibration time regardless of water saturation level. Similarly, 24 h was sufficient for kaolinite samples with 100% saturation exhibiting little isotopic variance even after 168 h of equilibration. For saturated silty loam with 2% organic carbon content, 96 h was the optimal equilibration time, whereas saturated silty loam with 4% organic carbon content did not reach isotopic equilibrium by 168 h. The optimal equilibration time increased depending on whether soil samples were disaggregated or kept in a core cutter. Inconclusive results for silty soils with organic carbon revealed the need to further investigate the possible influence of organic carbon, A-3293 on the DLVE method.

1. Introduction

The hydrogen and oxygen stable isotopes of water ($\delta^2\text{H}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$) are used to trace water in the hydrological cycle. In the absence of piezometers or lysimeters, porewater cannot be sampled directly and needs to be extracted from soil, sediment, or geologic samples typically using laboratory-based water extraction techniques such as high-speed centrifugation, azeotropic distillation (Allison and Hughes, 1983), cryogenic micro-distillation (Araguas-Araguas et al., 1995), microwave distillation (Munksgaard et al., 2014), mechanical squeezing (White et al., 1985), cryogenic vacuum extraction (Koeniger et al., 2011), and the accelerated solvent extraction technique (Zhu et al., 2014). However, a review by Kelln et al. (2001) showed large differences in porewater isotopic composition obtained from clay-rich soils using centrifugation, mechanical squeezing and azeotropic distillation

methods. Inter-laboratory comparisons further revealed large discrepancies between measured $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ values using different liquid water extraction methods (Orlowski et al., 2018; Beyer et al., 2020). Hence, different porewater extraction methods lead to incomparable isotopic compositions, which emphasizes the need for sound and adoptable measurement protocols. As an alternative to liquid water extraction methods, porewater can be proxy-analyzed in the laboratory by using the direct liquid–vapor equilibration (DLVE) method and laser-based spectrometry (Wassenaar et al. 2008). Apart from laboratory analysis, in-situ equilibration of porewater was also developed using gas-permeable tubes or soil gas probes for soils (Rothfuss et al., 2013; Gaj et al., 2016) or using porous probes for analyzing isotopes in tree xylem water (Volkman et al., 2016).

The DLVE method is based on the equilibration between soil porewater, and water vapor contained in the headspace of a closed sealable

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bag (Wassenaar et al., 2008). Briefly, liquid water used as standards or soil samples are equilibrated at constant temperature in re-sealable collapsible plastic Ziploc® bags filled with dry air. After 24–72 h, the fully equilibrated, 100% relative humidity vapor headspace is analyzed as an isotopic proxy for the liquid porewater using cavity ring down spectroscopy (CRDS) or off-axis integrated cavity output spectroscopy (OA-ICOS).

The isotopic equilibration time in the Ziploc® bags is affected by the soil texture, soil volume, soil chemistry, soil saturation level, and soil sampling method (Wassenaar et al., 2008; Gaj et al., 2018; Gaj and McDonnell, 2019; Wang et al., 2019; Hendry et al., 2013). The soil matric potential was found to influence the isotopic equilibrium fractionation factor of differently textured soil samples stored for only 24 h before analysis (Gaj et al., 2018; Gaj and McDonnell, 2019). While liquid water needs <10 min to reach full water–vapor isotopic equilibrium in Ziploc® bags at 22 °C (Wassenaar et al., 2008), the equilibration time for soil samples is longer and depends on soil texture. For example, clayey soils with low hydraulic conductivity take considerably longer to reach porewater–vapor isotopic equilibrium compared to sandy soil of higher hydraulic conductivity (Wassenaar et al., 2008). Previous studies used equilibration times ranging from hours to several days, and no standardized protocol for different soil or sediment samples exists yet. Garvelmann et al. (2012) equilibrated soil samples for 15 h for sandy and silty loam texture. Müller et al. (2014) equilibrated samples for 15 h in laminated polyester bags using different soil texture from two steep hillslopes in the Central Alps, Switzerland. Different soil texture (fluvial gravel, coarse sand, silt, silty loam, loam, and clayey loam) from three study sites in temperate central Europe were equilibrated for 48 h by Sprenger et al. (2015). Hendry et al. (2013) obtained an accurate porewater isotopic composition of fine-textured soil samples by equilibrating Cretaceous sediments for seven days. Additionally, Wang et al. (2019) found that 12–24 h were sufficient to reach an equilibrium in Ziploc® bags for soils with different clay and water content.

Initially, Wassenaar et al. (2008) suggested that sand with $\leq 5\%$ gravimetric water content and consolidated shale were unsuitable for the DLVE method as evaporative isotopic enrichment in $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ in the headspace vapor of Ziploc® bags was observed during longer equilibration time. Additionally, Wang et al. (2019) observed isotopic enrichment of oxygen and hydrogen isotopes for dry soil samples with different clay contents. To restrict isotopic enrichment induced by the diffusion of water vapor out of the bag, Hendry et al. (2015) suggested increasing the sample size to buffer evaporation enrichment in the remaining porewater. Wang et al. (2019) and Orłowski et al. (2016) showed that clay and water content must also be considered for the conversion and calibration of the water vapor isotopic composition into the porewater isotopic composition. Contrary to previous findings, Gaj et al. (2016) obtained porewater isotope measurements with good precision ($\delta^{18}\text{O} < 0.8\%$, $\delta^2\text{H} < 2.5\%$) for medium sand soils with <1 vol% soil water content in a semi-arid region in Namibia using water–vapor equilibration techniques with two different laser spectrometers (OA-ICOS and CRDS). These studies altogether indicate that the potential and concomitant influences of different soil textures and saturation levels on isotopic enrichment in equilibration bags needs to be further explored. This should be done to gain a better understanding of how to reliably measure soil samples using the DLVE method.

The use of resealable inflatable plastic bags also revealed technical problems from minor water vapor loss out of the bags through diffusive transport and back-diffusion of vapor from laboratory air into the bags (Wassenaar et al., 2008; Hendry et al., 2015). Low-cost plastic freezer bags with double zipper seals were initially used but were vulnerable to leakage and evaporative loss (Wassenaar et al., 2008). Double bagging greatly improved this, and later investigation by Hendry et al. (2015) showed water loss from Ziploc® bags, crystal clear bags, and IsoPak were larger than from Mylar, black bags, and silver pouches. The latter, albeit more costly, are preferable for up to 50 days of sample storage and avoiding water loss. Additionally, Mattei et al. (2019) found that large

re-usable Fold-A-Carrier Reliance™ plastic carboys allowed 30 days of sample storage, albeit at a higher cost of 10 USD/bag. However, it was observed that resealable bags which were too airtight did not allow spectrally interfering biogenic gases to escape. Biogenic gas buildup is produced *in-situ* during long equilibration times, and negatively interferes with the laser isotope spectral analyses (Gralher et al., 2018; Hendry et al. 2011). Interferences from biogenic carbon dioxide (CO_2) can be corrected by using sensitivity spectral features recorded with the CRDS analyzers (Gralher et al., 2018). Thus, it appears that low-cost Ziploc® plastic freezer bags are sufficiently airtight to allow for water isotope analysis performed within 10 days before evaporative loss becomes apparent while at the same time minimizing biogenic gas buildup (Hendry et al., 2015).

In most studies, the DLVE method is operationally carried out using different (i) sample storage bags, (ii) soil sample sizes, (iii) treatment procedures and (iv) equilibration times (Hendry et al., 2015; Orłowski et al., 2016; Gralher et al., 2018; Gaj et al. 2018; Gaj and McDonnell, 2019; Gralher et al. 2021). However, it remains unclear how different saturation levels and equilibration times affect the isotopic analyses of porewater in soils having different physicochemical characteristics. Thus, to investigate the effect of varying soil textures and saturation levels on the porewater–vapor equilibration process in a closed system, a series of laboratory experiments were conducted. Different soil samples (sandy, silty loam, and clay) with varied saturation levels (100%, 80%, 60% and 40%) were equilibrated for different times under isothermal conditions. This study aims at improving our understanding on the application and possible limitations of the DLVE method to analyze the stable isotopic composition of soil porewater.

2. Methods

2.1. Soil material

Four different soil samples with different chemical and physical properties were studied (Table 1). Sandy soil free of organic carbon was obtained from a gravel pit in Bruckmühl near Munich, Germany. Based on laboratory dry sieving, the sample consisted of 10% fine sand, 31% medium sand, 28% coarse sand, and 30% fine gravel; clay and silt accounted for ca. 1%. The silty loam samples were topsoil from two different field sites in Lower Austria, one being Mistelbach and the other Obersiebenbrunn. Based on wet sieving and sedimentation, the soil from Mistelbach consisted of 11% sand, 64% silt, and 25% clay while soil from Obersiebenbrunn was made up of 25% sand, 63% silt, and 12% clay. The total organic carbon content of soil from Mistelbach and Obersiebenbrunn were 2% and 4% respectively, analyzed with the Walkley-Black chromic acid wet oxidation method. The fourth sample was powdered kaolinite (Orange kaolin) free of organic material from Carl Roth GmbH as a proxy for soil samples with high clay content. Kaolinite was preferred over other clay groups as it is commonly found in soil and has low plasticity. Due to its low plasticity, soil will not deform easily during sample handling. Kaolinite also has a low-swelling capacity compared to other types of clay soils (Foster, 1954). It took less time to saturate and could be handled with less effort for analysis, especially using 40% saturation level.

2.2. Sample preparation and analysis

Three kg of each soil sample with different textures were oven-dried for three days at 105 °C. Un-sieved dried samples were placed into 1L volume cylinders and brought to 100%, 80%, 60% and 40% saturation level using different volumes of water. In order to determine the amount of water needed to reach each saturation level, the soil bulk density and porosity of each individual sample was calculated during sample preparation. This calculation was done using the mass of the oven-dried sample and the volume occupied in the 1L cylinder. Then, the specific soil porosity of each soil sample in each cylinder was obtained from the

Table 1
Soil properties of samples used in this study.

No.	Soil origin	Soil texture	Gravel (%)	Sand (%)	Silt (%)	Clay (%)	Total organic carbon (%)
1.	Gravel pit, Bruckmühl, Munich, Germany	Sandy	30	69	0.5	0.5	0
2.	Natural topsoil, Mistelbach, Austria	Silty loam	0	11	64	25	2
3.	Natural topsoil, Obersiebenbrunn, Austria	Silty loam	0	25	63	12	4
4.	Pure kaolinite, Carl Roth GmbH	Clay	0	0	0	100	0

calculated individual soil bulk density and an assumed particle density of 2.65 g/cm^3 .

The sample saturation process was done using water of known isotopic composition ($\delta^{18}\text{O} = -11.2\text{‰} \pm 0\text{‰}$, $\delta^2\text{H} = -77.8\text{‰} \pm 0.1\text{‰}$). Water was applied slowly and close to the surface of the soil from the top of the 1L volume cylinders. To prevent evaporative losses, the cylinders were immediately and tightly covered with aluminum foil after the introduced water had infiltrated. While it cannot be guaranteed that aluminum foil fully blocked evaporation, the soil water isotopic composition was later measured to detect any possible changes from the original infiltration water (see next paragraph for the exact procedure using rhizon samplers). The advance of the wetting front was observed to be larger in sandy soil compared to the silty soil or kaolinite. These saturated soils were left for seven days at a constant laboratory temperature ($22 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) to allow the introduced water to move through gravitation and adhesion along the soil pores in the cylinder.

Next, each soil sample was individually mixed and four replicates of approximately 200–250 g soil of each saturation level were broken into small aggregates and placed individually in Ziploc® brand Double Guard freezer bags with Double Zipper Seal (ca. 1 L volume) (S. C. Johnson & Sons Inc., USA). Additionally, four replicates of 100% saturated soil samples were placed in 200 cm^3 core cutters and sealed at the bottom using lids, allowing only the top surface of the soil samples to be exposed to liquid–vapor exchange in the Ziploc® bags. This sampling method using core cutters was carried out only for 100% saturated soil samples to investigate the effect of the exposed soil surface area on the liquid–vapor exchange process in Ziploc® bags. Each plastic sample bag was then inflated with dry atmospheric air and sealed quickly for water–vapor equilibration. The initial mass (m_1) of the inflated Ziploc® bags with soil samples was weighed and recorded using a mass balance ($\pm 0.01 \text{ g}$). The weighed inflated Ziploc® bags were double-bagged using Toppits® brand freezer bags (ca. 3 L volume) (Melitta Gesellschaft GmbH, Salzburg, Austria). The final mass (m_2) of the Ziploc® bags after sample storage and before headspace analysis were weighed and recorded to determine gravimetric water loss from the individual Ziploc® bags during the time of equilibration. The different soil samples with variable water saturation levels were left to equilibrate and analyzed for headspace stable isotopic composition of water vapor after 24 h, 48 h, 72 h, 96 h, and 168 h. Rhizon samplers (Rhizon CSS 3 cm female Luer-Lock, Rhizosphere Research Products B.V., Wageningen, The Netherlands) were used to extract four replicates of 1 mL of soil porewater from the remaining saturated soils in the 1L cylinders which were not sampled for the DLVE method to obtain the initial water isotopic composition before equilibration (reference water, δ_i). Briefly, rhizon samplers are thin, perforated rods of a microfiltration membrane with a nominal pore size of 0.12–0.18 μm . They are constructed of hydrophilic membranes consisting of a blend of polyvinylpyrrolidone and polyethersulfone (Rhizosphere.com, 2021). To minimize potential isotope fractionation during soil sampling, rhizon samplers were vertically inserted into the saturated soil samples and porewater was sampled from the middle soil depths instead nearer to the soil surface or bottom part. After insertion, a 10 mL syringe was connected to each sampler via a Luer-Lock connection. The plunger was pulled, and a low-pressure condition was created in the syringe. The first 1 mL of the water was discarded from each syringe, and 4 mL of porewater samples were collected (Geris et al., 2015; Steiner et al., 2018). The extracted liquid porewaters were stored in replicates in 1 mL septum-capped glass vials

for stable isotope analysis. Additionally, two control experiments were done to determine potential isotopic fractionation effects caused by extracting water using rhizon samplers. The first control experiment compared the isotopic composition of four replicates of tap water in a laboratory beaker (without soil) that was extracted using rhizon samplers with the isotopic composition of tap water directly sampled into glass vials. If no significant isotopic differences were found, isotopic fractionation by the porous ceramic tip of the rhizon samplers could be considered negligible. In the second control experiment, a comparison was made between four replicates of the measured $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ values of rhizon-extracted soil porewater and the isotopic composition of soil porewater as determined by the DLVE method in 100% saturated soil conditions. If no significant differences were found, fully saturated soil did not cause fractionation during extraction of porewater with rhizon samplers. Finally, if both control experiments show that rhizon samplers do not cause isotope fractionation during sampling, the rhizon-sampled porewater will be the reference water δ_i , representative of the soil porewater.

As the oxygen and hydrogen isotopic fractionation by liquid–vapor equilibration is highly temperature dependent (Majoube, 1971), the sample preparation and analysis were conducted isothermally at $22 \pm 0.5 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, and all standards were treated the same way. To ensure reproducibility, the headspace vapor analysis of each sample was systematically started at the same time every day and finished within 174 min (20 samples (five times four replicates) and nine standards with about six minutes each). Analyses were also conducted in an identical sequence of 100%, 80%, 60%, and 40%-saturation, followed by samples in core cutters.

The isotopic composition of porewater calculated from the four replicates of each soil texture and saturation level combination was averaged (δ_f) and standard deviations (SD) were determined. The difference $\Delta\delta^{18}\text{O} = \delta_f - \delta_i$ was calculated and evaluated, with positive $\Delta\delta^{18}\text{O}$ indicating an isotopic enrichment of the sample compared to its reference water, while negative $\Delta\delta^{18}\text{O}$ indicates isotopic depletion of porewater. $\Delta\delta^{18}\text{O}$ values larger and lower than instrumental uncertainty (next section) suggested insufficient time for porewater to reach isotopic equilibrium with the headspace vapor in the bags. Possible main causes of isotope effects are soil matrix forces between the pore-bound water and the water vapor phase in soil that eventually became the measured headspace water vapor, vapor diffusion loss through the Ziploc® bags, or back-diffusion of laboratory air into the Ziploc® bags. Bag seal leakage was not considered as an effect, since a seal-leaking bag quickly and obviously deflated.

2.3. Laboratory analysis

A CRDS laser spectroscope (Picarro L2130-I, Picarro, Inc., Santa Clara, CA, USA) was used to measure the isotopic composition of the headspace water vapor of soil samples and liquid water samples. The accuracy of the CRDS analyzer for vapor analyses was $\pm 1.0\text{‰}$ for $\delta^2\text{H}$ and $\pm 0.5\text{‰}$ for $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ (Picarro, Inc., 2020). The $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ values are reported in per mil (‰) relative to Vienna Standard Mean Ocean Water (VSMOW) (Craig, 1961). Following the protocol of Wassenaar et al. (2008), two in-house standard waters with known liquid isotopic composition ($\delta^{18}\text{O} = -11.2\text{‰} \pm 0.1\text{‰}$, $\delta^2\text{H} = -77.2\text{‰} \pm 0.7\text{‰}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O} = -6.3\text{‰} \pm 0\text{‰}$, $\delta^2\text{H} = -47.9\text{‰} \pm 0.1\text{‰}$) were measured between two samples in the sequence of standard 1, sample 1, sample 2, and standard

2 for drift correction and normalization. The headspace vapor was sampled for approximately 6 min and the final 60 s of the $\delta^2\text{H}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ readings were averaged provided the standard deviation was $<0.5\text{‰}$ for $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $<1.0\text{‰}$ for $\delta^2\text{H}$.

3. Results

We first briefly discuss rhizon sampler results, as it is important to verify that rhizon-sampled porewater can be used as a reference and thus the $\Delta\delta$ values of the main results of this study are valid. From the first control experiment, tap water from a laboratory beaker (without soil) extracted using rhizon samplers showed negligible isotope fractionation effects with differences of $\pm 0.1\text{‰}$ for $\delta^2\text{H}$ and 0‰ for $\delta^{18}\text{O}$. This means that the rhizon samplers themselves did not cause isotope fractionation. The second control experiment determined whether the isotopic compositions of rhizon-sampled water of 100% saturated soil and from DLVE-measured porewater differed. It showed only small $\Delta\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\Delta\delta^2\text{H}$ ($\pm 0.2\text{‰}$ $\Delta\delta^2\text{H}$ and $\pm 0.1\text{‰}$ $\Delta\delta^{18}\text{O}$), indicating a good comparability of rhizon-sampled porewater and results of the DLVE method at 100% saturation. However, there were differences between rhizon-sampled porewater and the initial tap water for all soil textures and saturation levels. Rhizon-sampled porewater of silty soil with 4% organic carbon had isotopic differences of $+2.1\text{‰}$ for $\Delta\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $+10.2\text{‰}$ for $\Delta\delta^2\text{H}$, and the rest of the soil samples had isotopic differences of $<0.4\text{‰}$ for $\Delta\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $<1.4\text{‰}$ for $\Delta\delta^2\text{H}$ from the initial tap water. Thus, independent of soil texture or saturation level, only silty soil with 4% organic carbon showed large deviations from tap water when extracting porewater with rhizon samplers. Compared to the first control experiment with only pure water being extracted from a laboratory beaker, we assume that specifically silty soil with 4% organic carbon (and possibly specifically this sample for unknown reasons)

influenced the isotopic composition, and not any soil in general. In context of the second control experiments that showed no difference between DLVE measurements and rhizon samplers at 100% saturation, the DLVE method would also be prone to the same effect. A possible explanation is that the rhizon-sampled porewater cannot be assumed to represent the water of the entire pore space, but rather that of larger pores which are accessible to the rhizon samplers' relatively low suction head. Other studies using different water extraction techniques such as cryogenic extraction (Orlowski et al., 2013), azeotropic, vacuum and microdistillation methods (Walker et al., 1994; Araguás-Araguás et al., 1995) have also reported difficulties of obtaining the "true" isotopic composition (meaning here: the isotopic composition of the spiking water) when extracting porewater, which might be due to different water pools being sampled at different suction heads. However, the fact that in the present study larger isotopic differences only appeared for silty soil with 4% organic carbon indicated either the influence of organic matter on stable water isotopes (see Discussion section), or other unknown factors specific to this soil sample as silty soil with 2% organic carbon was not affected. There might also be a threshold value of organic carbon content necessary to significantly affect the isotopic composition. As the exact reason does however remain unclear, the rhizon-sampled porewater was accepted as the reference water δ_i for all soil samples with the caveat that results of silty soil with 4% organic carbon should be considered with caution.

3.1. Saturation effect

Overall, the ranges of $\Delta\delta^{18}\text{O}$ for the four saturation levels were low for sandy soil (-1.1‰ to 0‰) and kaolinite (-0.5‰ to 1.2‰) (Fig. 1). Repeated measurements showed similar standard deviations for sandy soil ($\pm 0.9\text{‰}$ to $\pm 0.1\text{‰}$) and kaolinite ($\pm 0.8\text{‰}$ to $\pm 0.1\text{‰}$). 24 h was

Fig. 1. $\Delta\delta^{18}\text{O}$ (‰) versus equilibration time (hours) for (a) 100%, (b) 80%, (c) 60%, and (d) 40% saturated sandy, kaolinite and two silty soils with 4% and 2% organic carbon (OC). The two grey dashed lines represent the uncertainty limits of the isotope analyzer.

sufficient for porewater of sandy soil and kaolinite to reach isotopic equilibrium with the headspace vapor for most saturation levels, except for 40%-saturated kaolinite. Compared to sand and kaolinite, silty soil with 2% organic carbon content generally had large $\Delta\delta^{18}\text{O}$ (-1.0‰ to 4.3‰) and SD ($\pm 0.2\text{‰}$ to $\pm 3.1\text{‰}$) for all saturation levels and equilibration times. Similarly, silty soil with 4% carbon content had larger $\Delta\delta^{18}\text{O}$ (-0.2‰ to 6.6‰) and SD ($\pm 0.1\text{‰}$ to $\pm 8.0\text{‰}$) in comparison to all tested soil samples. With few exceptions, all $\delta^2\text{H}$ results were comparable to $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ results (Fig. 2). For example, the deviation of 80%-saturated sandy soil for 96 h equilibration time was more pronounced in the case of $\delta^2\text{H}$. While $\Delta\delta^2\text{H}$ results of kaolinite fell within measurement uncertainty (except for 40% saturation), the silty soils deviated from the rhizon-sampled porewater.

3.2. Surface area effect

Fig. 3 shows the effect of different equilibration times on $\Delta\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\Delta\delta^2\text{H}$ values for 100%-saturated soil samples that were placed into core cutters. For sandy soil and both silty soils, the average $\Delta\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\Delta\delta^2\text{H}$ fell outside our uncertainty limit throughout the 168 h of equilibration. Silty soil with 2% organic carbon had the highest average $\Delta\delta^{18}\text{O}$ ($\Delta\delta^2\text{H}$) compared to the other tested soil samples. Only kaolinite had $\Delta\delta^{18}\text{O}$ ($\Delta\delta^2\text{H}$) values of $0.1\text{‰} \pm 0.2\text{‰}$ ($0.7\text{‰} \pm 0.3\text{‰}$) within the uncertainty range for up to 72 h. For longer equilibration times, $\Delta\delta^{18}\text{O}$ ($\Delta\delta^2\text{H}$) values exceeded the uncertainty limits for kaolinite samples. In general, the $\Delta\delta^{18}\text{O}$ ($\Delta\delta^2\text{H}$) of all 100%-saturated soil samples placed in core cutters were larger than for loose soil samples.

3.3. Water loss effect

The average water loss from the Ziploc® bags was low (0–0.3%) with

small SD values ranging from $\pm 0\%$ to $\pm 0.1\%$ for up to 168 h of equilibration time for all soil textures and saturation levels (Fig. 4 and Fig. 5). The average water loss increased with equilibration time independent of soil texture and saturation level and did not influence $\Delta\delta^{18}\text{O}$ or $\Delta\delta^2\text{H}$. Additionally, the average $\Delta\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\Delta\delta^2\text{H}$ covered a larger range of values when the saturation level was lower, even though the water losses from Ziploc® bags were $< 0.2\%$.

4. Discussion

Sandy soil and kaolinite, and two different silty soils with 2% and 4% organic carbon content were used to study the influence of soil textures and saturation levels on the isotopic equilibration time in Ziploc® bags prior to analysis using a laser spectrometer to determine the porewater isotopic composition. The fraction of water loss caused by diffusion processes was $< 0.3\%$. Substantial ($> 2\%$) loss of water would lead to enriched isotopic values due to kinetic isotope fractionation after 240–360 h (Hendry et al., 2015). As the water loss from the Ziploc® bags was $< 2\%$ and samples were double-bagged, we assumed negligible kinetic isotope fractionation caused by possible diffusion and back-diffusion processes, which did not influence the oxygen and hydrogen isotope measurements. Also, as both $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ outcomes were similar, there was no indication of substantial influence of kinetic isotope fractionation processes. We conclude that Ziploc® bags are effective for short-term sample equilibrations up to a week. Compared to Ziploc® bags, Gralher et al. (2021) found that Toppits® brand freezer bags were unacceptable for the DLVE method due to excessive water vapor loss owing to thin plastic walls and high degradation of the bag material from UV effects. Although Ziploc® bags are food-grade and not certified to be zipper-seal leak-tight, changes in $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ were presumably either caused by effects related to soil properties or

Fig. 2. $\Delta\delta^2\text{H}$ (‰) versus equilibration time (hours) for (a) 100%, (b) 80%, (c) 60%, and (d) 40% saturated sandy, kaolinite and two silty soils with 4% and 2% organic carbon (OC). The two grey dashed lines represent the uncertainty limits of the isotope analyzer.

Fig. 3. (a) $\Delta\delta^{18}\text{O}$ (‰) and (b) $\Delta\delta^2\text{H}$ (‰) versus equilibration time for 100%-saturated sandy, kaolinite, and two silty soils with 4% and 2% organic carbon (OC) placed in 200 cm³ core cutter rings. The two grey dashed lines represent the uncertainty limits of the isotope analyzer.

Fig. 4. $\Delta\delta^{18}\text{O}$ (‰) versus water loss (%) for (a) 100%, (b) 80%, (c) 60%, and (d) 40% saturated sandy, kaolinite and two silty soils with 4% and 2% organic carbon (OC). The two grey dashed lines represent the uncertainty limits of the isotope analyzer.

saturation level, or both.

The initial DLVE study of [Wassenaar et al. \(2008\)](#) investigated intact clay-rich sediment cores with low permeability and found an optimum equilibration time was 72–96 h to avoid evaporative enrichment due to vapor leakage, which became apparent not until 288 h of equilibration time. They assumed soils of high permeability would require less equilibration time, and the results of our study confirm this, as sand needed only 24 h to reach isotopic equilibrium regardless of water saturation level. Surprisingly, kaolinite equilibrated within 24 h too and maintained isotopic equilibrium up to 168 h. The only exception was 40%-saturated kaolinite, but the $\Delta\delta^{18}\text{O}$ for those samples were still close to the measurement uncertainty of $\pm 0.5\text{‰}$ (Fig. 1). This might indicate

that with even lower saturation levels, kaolinite $\Delta\delta^{18}\text{O}$ could increase further beyond the measurement uncertainty. However, [Wang et al. \(2019\)](#) analyzed clay-rich samples with a gravimetric water content as low as 5% (0.05 g g^{-1}) and found they equilibrated within 24 h. Even if both indicate dry soil, the gravimetric water content and saturation level are not directly comparable, and further experiments with lower saturation levels are needed to conclude if kaolinite will equilibrate within 24 h or not, to confirm the findings of [Wang et al. \(2019\)](#). We initially expected a difference in equilibration time between sand and clay due to their different matric forces as [Gaj et al. \(2016\)](#) showed high matric forces of intact soil slow down the water-vapor equilibration process. However, the soils used in this study and [Wang et al. \(2019\)](#) were

Fig. 5. $\Delta\delta^2\text{H}$ (‰) versus water loss (%) for (a) 100%, (b) 80%, (c) 60%, and (d) 40% saturated sandy, kaolinite and two silty soils with 4% and 2% organic carbon (OC). The two grey dashed lines represent the uncertainty limits of the isotope analyzer.

disaggregated/sieved to <2 mm, respectively. This likely created a larger surface-to-volume ratio of porewater exposed to the headspace water vapor. Molecular diffusion thus enabled liquid-vapor/isotopic equilibrium to be reached in a short time, thereby possibly eliminating the effect of soil texture. Silt, however, reacted differently and did not equilibrate isotopically within 24 h. A major difference between the silt samples and sand or clay was the presence of particulate organic carbon (discussed later). We recommend sieving or breaking down solid samples into smaller pieces to measure the porewater isotopic composition as precisely and quickly as possible. Our results suggest that Ziploc® bags can be used to store samples for up to 168 h without isotopic enrichment for sandy and clay soils free of organic carbon.

Contrary to sandy and clay soils free of organic carbon, the two silty samples with 2% and 4% organic carbon contents behaved inconsistently, reaching, and departing from isotopic equilibrium at seemingly random hours of equilibration time. Since silt is a particle size fraction between sand and clay, this behavior was unexpected. The presence of organic carbon content in both silty samples compared to sandy and clay soils might have interfered with the equilibration process. As shown by Gaj and McDonnell (2019), the presence of particulate organic matter in soils influenced the isotopic equilibrium fractionation by increasing the rate of liquid-vapor exchange processes which were attributed to changes in the soil hydraulic conductivity and solid interfacial chemistry. Orłowski et al. (2016) also showed that increasing organic matter content negatively impacts the isotopic measurements of physically extracted soil water. However, they used the cryogenic extraction method and not the DLVE method as in the present study and results may differ. Our results using the DLVE method showed that $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ values of both silty soils could have been similarly affected by the presence of sedimentary organic carbon. Weak organic acids ($-\text{COOH}$) in organic carbon contain exchangeable hydrogen atoms that cannot be removed easily but react readily with water molecules (Meißner et al., 2014), and this can cause significant isotopic deviation between the

reference and measured isotopic composition of water isotopes. While the deviations of $\delta^2\text{H}$ (Fig. 2) would fit this hypothesis, $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ also showed similar behavior which cannot be explained by $-\text{COOH}$ functional groups (Fig. 1). The impact of organic carbon on the DLVE method requires further study to understand the processes potentially causing isotopic fractionation.

Spiking oven-dried soil with isotopic reference water is the most widely used technique to determine the performances and accuracy of the DLVE method. Thielemann et al. (2019) and Gaj et al. (2016) speculated that oven-drying soil samples at 105 °C does not completely remove the residual water, which in turn can cause an isotope exchange between soil-bound water and reference water particularly in fine textured soils when the oven-dried soil is rewetted with reference water. This could explain the measured $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ values of soil water in silty soils that deviated from the reference water (Figs. 1 and 2) values, since those samples were taken from field sites. It is possible that the residual water that entered the soil prior to sampling was bound in the smaller pores and not removed by standard oven drying. This might be relevant for silty soils because the residual water content for sand is (close to) zero, and the kaolinite was a dry powder.

Compared to the broken-down soil samples, samples packed in core cutters took considerably longer to reach isotopic equilibrium, if at all (Fig. 3). The increase in equilibration time might have been caused by the smaller soil surface area exposed to liquid-vapor exchange compared to broken-down soil. The reduced surface area in contact with the headspace limited the water vapor diffusion out of the soil by limiting the available pathways for diffusion (less surface area in contact with the air, less pathways ending at the soil-air-interface). Of all samples tested with the core cutters, only kaolinite attained isotopic equilibrium after 72 h, while the rest of soil samples had enriched isotopic compositions. The fact that only kaolinite reached equilibrium could have been because clay has the comparatively highest porosity and surface area of saturated pore spaces (Carman, 1939) exposed to the

atmosphere in the Ziploc® bags for liquid–vapor exchange. Saturation levels <100% were not tested in the present study with core cutters, and results might be different when using drier soil samples.

The isotopic deviations of aggregated silty soils with organic carbon were larger than sandy soil and kaolinite free of organic carbon, similar to the results observed when the soils were broken down. Hence, regardless of water saturation level or sampling technique, the presence of organic carbon appears to be a limitation to the application for the DLVE and all other water extraction methods.

The results from this study are a step towards achieving better protocols of equilibration time of different soils depending on their saturation level using the DLVE method. For sand and clay free of organic carbon, the equilibration time can be reduced to 24 h, or samples can be stored up to 168 h. The presence of sedimentary organic carbon regardless of its concentration level remains a serious issue for all approaches where organic carbon removal techniques cannot be practically applied. This finding supports the study by Oerter and Bowen (2017) in which *in-situ* isotope measurements of sandy loam showed isotopic enrichment in soil with >2% organic materials (mulch). A possible explanation was given by Lin and Horita (2016) who found less isotopic fractionation when porewater equilibrated with ambient air compared to bulk water equilibrating with it, which they argued was due to hydrophilic interactions between porewater and soil particles. As organic matter could also interact with the porewater, the isotopic fractionation might have been affected in this study.

5. Summary and conclusion

Our findings suggest that for disaggregated sandy soils with saturation levels as low as 40%, 24 h of equilibration time was sufficient when using Ziploc® bags with the DLVE method. 24 h sufficed also for loose kaolinite up to 60% saturation, but 48 h was required when the saturation level was reduced to 40%. By contrast, silty soil with 2% organic carbon content behaved erratically, seemingly reaching equilibrium at random. Loose silty soil with 4% organic carbon on the other hand did not reach isotopic equilibrium. Based on comparison measurements with soils put into core cutters, we recommend that samples be broken down into smaller aggregates to reduce the time required for reaching equilibrium. Ziploc® bags were shown to exhibit no evaporative impact on $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ up to 168 h, and hence are suitable short-term sample storage and equilibration bags. Deviations of both $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ were found that might have been influenced by organic carbon in the two silty loam soils, but the exact reasons remain unknown. Further research is needed to understand the influence of soil organic carbon on isotopic measurements using the DLVE method.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Devakunjari Vadibeler: Conceptualization, Investigation, Methodology, Validation, Visualization, Writing - original draft and review.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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